

THE EFFECTS OF 14-BENZOYLKARAKOLINE ON CONTRACTIVE ACTIVITY OF RAT AORTA SMOOTH MUSCLE CELLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684055>

Abstract. It was investigated how 14-benzoylkarakoline affected the rat aortic smooth muscle cells' ability to contract. According to the results, rat aorta preparations that had been constricted by the beta-adrenergic receptor agonist phenylephrine are successfully relaxed by 14-O-BK. It can be deduced that the relaxant effect of the studied alkaloid is caused by the suppression of the transport of Ca²⁺ ions at the SR level in light of the fact that the contractions induced by this antagonist are primarily caused by the activation of the release of Ca²⁺ ions from the SR through IP₃R.

Keywords: smooth muscles, sarkoplazmic reticulum, aorta, phenylephrine, Ca²⁺ channel, 14-benzoylkarakoline.

Introduction Cardiovascular disease is one of the most common pathologies and today occupies one of the first places among the mortality and disability of the population of the developed countries of the world [1]. According to modern data, in the development of diseases of the cardiovascular system, there are violations of the contractile activity of smooth muscle cells (SMC), vascular tone, transport of Ca²⁺ ions [2]. In this regard, one of the most urgent tasks of modern medicine is the development of new approaches to adequate treatment of arterial hypertension, based on the latest advances in molecular pharmacology.

The purpose of the study: to characterize the effect of the alkaloid 14-benzoyl karakoline on the transport of Ca²⁺ ions in the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR). 14-benzoylkarakoline (14-BK), a derivative of diterpenoid alkaloid karakoline, isolated from *Aconitum karakolicum*, has been reported to possess diverse pharmacological properties, including spasmolytic, antiarrhythmic and anesthetic activities [3].

Materials and Methods Tissue Preparation. All experimental protocols and conditions for preoperative care were approved by the animal use committee of our institution. Adult male Wistar rats weighing 200 – 250 g were anesthetized with sodium pentobarbital and their thorax was opened and the thoracic aorta was quickly removed and immediately placed in Krebs solution contained (in mmol/l); 118 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 25 mM NaHCO₃, 1.2 mM MgSO₄, 2 mM CaCl₂, 1.2 mM KH₂PO₄, 11 mM glucose. All the dissection procedures were performed with extreme care to protect the endothelium from inadvertent damage. The aorta was cleaned of adipose and connective tissue and cut into rings (2–3 mm long) [4].

Results and Discussion: In the past, we discovered that the diterpenoid alkaloids talatizamine and 14-benzoylkarakoline may successfully relax rat aortic preparations that had been previously constrictive due to the presence of norepinephrine and hyperkalium solutions. In our experiments, PE (1 μM) in the presence of verapamil (0.1 μM) induced aortic contractions, the strength of which was 10,9 ± 2,3% less than the force of contractions caused by it in the absence of verapamil. Under these circumstances, the addition of 14-BK alkaloid significantly reduced the force of PE-induced aortic contractions, which fell by 62.7 ± 4.1% of the control, respectively.

The results indicate that the observed effect of the studied alkaloid may be due to the blockade of receptor-gated Ca²⁺ channels. This is confirmed by experiments with the blocker of α-phenadrenergic receptors - phentolamine, in the occurrence of which the effect of the

alkaloid 14-BK on FA-induced short aorta decreased by $45.2 \pm 3.8\%$, respectively, from the control obtained in the absence of phentolamine (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Effect of phentolamine (10µM) on the relaxant effect of 14-BK (*p<0.05, **p<0.01; n=5).

These findings suggest that the receptor-gated Ca^{2+} channel blockage may also contribute to the relaxing effects of the 14-BK alkaloid. Thus, analysis of the data obtained in these experiments shows that the alkaloid 14-BK effectively relaxes rat aortic preparations previously reduced by the α -adrenergic receptor agonist phenylephrine.

References

1. Roth G.A., Johnson C., Abajobir A., et al. Global, regional and national burden of cardiovascular diseases for 10 causes, 1990 to 2015. // J. Am. Coll. Cardiol. – 2017. – V.70. – P.1-25.
2. Wright P., Thomas M. Pathophysiology and management of heart failure // Clinical Pharmacist. – 2018. – V.10 (12). – P.261-269.
3. Djakhangirov F.N., et al., Diterpenoid alkaloids as a new class of antiarrhythmic agents. Structure–activity relationship. Chem. Nat. Compd.1997, 33, 254-269. 262-263.
4. Mirzayeva Yu.T.et al., Characteristic of the vazorelaxant action of the talatizamine alkaloid and its derivatives // Journal of Pharmaceutics and Pharmacology Research. 2021, P. 1-5. 16192 Coastal Highway, Lewes, USA.